

1 **Drunken walking through the forest? On the importance of extreme variability in spatial**
2 **models of land use change.**

3 keywords: disruptive scenarios, uncertainty, demand variability; Markov chain; cellular
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7 **Abstract**

8 Transformative change in cities, landscapes and regions is typically anticipated through
9 computational simulation modelling of future land use scenarios based on estimated land-use
10 change trajectories. One of the greatest sources of uncertainty in such models is the amount of
11 land which is expected to change (land use demand), yet this is significantly underexplored.
12 Modellers often simply fix it at a plausible estimate, e.g. from population tendency projections or
13 policy targets, with only slight variations across very different hypothetical futures. We propose
14 an innovative approach to address this problem. We simulate extreme land-use demand
15 variability in future forest land allocation in Scotland, UK, using a stochastic Markov chain
16 known as a “drunkard’s walk”, coupled to a cellular automata land use model. The model reveals
17 problematic assumptions in Scotland’s Forestry Strategy, which anticipates 21% of Scotland’s
18 land area under Forestry by 2032. While the area target seems achievable, the timescale is
19 doubtful, since only very extreme variations in the Markov function (5% year on year) allow it to
20 be met by the specified dates, and then only <25% of the time. At the same time, simulations
21 under which the target is met produced runaway afforestation booms leading to loss of natural
22 areas and arable land. Outcomes like these, the chain of events which lead to them, and the
23 timescales on which they may occur, are not apparent from incremental land use demand models
24 or fixed demand scenarios. Our approach opens up new pathways for broader, more disruptive
25 scenarios of land use change.

26 **1. Introduction**

27 *1.1 Uncertainty in anticipatory models of future land use change.*

28 Computational land use simulation models are popular tools for anticipating future change in
29 cities, landscapes and regions, and are frequently intended to inform policy. Such models explore
30 complex dynamic interactions in the land system, e.g. between city transport networks and urban
31 expansion (Roman et al 2025), land use change and greenhouse gas emissions (Sohl et al 2012),
32 cropland expansion and water availability (Van Delden et al 2007), the dynamics of shifting
33 cultivation (Wickramisuriya et al 2009), *inter alia*, and typically use scenario-based approaches
34 to handle the high degree of uncertainty in simulation outcomes. However, potential variability is
35 often far greater than scenarios allow, especially for land uses whose dynamics are driven by
36 policy or economic stimuli (or both). Many authors have called for more diverse, exploratory

37 approaches to land use change modelling that are better able to cope with highly variable
38 outcomes (e.g. Alexander et al 2017, Roman et al 2025, Hewitt et al 2022).

39 While much attention has been dedicated to spatial variability in such models, the quantity of
40 land expected to change (land use demand), is arguably an even greater source of uncertainty but
41 is comparatively underexplored. Many examples around the world show that land use change
42 often occurs in sudden and surprising ways. Agricultural subsidy regimes have often led to
43 dramatic changes in cropland, with farmers switching crops *en masse* in unpredictable ways
44 (Winder et al 1998). Renewable energy subsidies have also led to dramatic land conversion to
45 renewable use, often in the space of just a few years. In Spain, for example, the solar energy
46 boom led to extraordinarily rapid development of solar farms, from an estimated mere 690 ha
47 recorded in 2005 to around 22,010 ha in 2011, an increase of 3,090% (Díaz Pacheco et al 2018).
48 A similar case can be found in the use of crops for biofuel, for example in Brazil or the United
49 States, where targeted subsidies led to an enormous land expansion and raised concerns about
50 competition with food crops (Rathmann et al 2010). Many countries have seen recent large-scale
51 forest expansion as a result of targeted national policy (Zhang 2019, Heilmayr et al 2020). EU
52 renewable energy policies, which until recently included bioenergy as a renewable energy
53 source, have also led to increased planting for direct conversion to wood energy in some areas
54 (Vogt et al 2022).

55 In this paper, we argue that models should respond to these dynamics in much more creative
56 ways than those typically found in the literature. We focus on uncertainty in land use demand
57 (*how much land to allocate*) which has been comparatively neglected in favour of uncertainty in
58 spatial allocation (*where will new land uses go*). Doing so allows us to account for a much
59 broader range of land use outcomes, including those which may *a priori* seem unrealistic. Only
60 in this way can highly disruptive outcomes, such as the complete loss of an important land use
61 type, or the total failure of a flagship policy, be properly anticipated.

62 1.2 Case study and research questions

63 To explore this issue we choose a simple case study and a single, current and well-understood
64 land use expansion dynamic, that of new forest planting (afforestation). Afforestation has
65 attracted the attention of policymakers around the world as an apparently reliable way to
66 compensate for carbon emissions from particular industries and sectors which face difficulties in
67 emissions reduction. Despite the currently rather controversial nature of forest carbon offsets (see
68 e.g. West et al 2023, Badgley et al 2022) the idea is attractive in principle. Many parts of the
69 world have suffered widespread deforestation in the past, with notable negative consequences. In
70 many countries forest expansion is already underway, for example in Spain, where concern over
71 widespread deforestation has led to major centralized reforestation efforts throughout most of the
72 20th century and beyond (Vadell et al 2016), and in the United Kingdom (UK), where private
73 commercial afforestation was extensively promoted through woodland grant schemes over a
74 similar time period (Burton et al 2018). Within the UK, Scotland, a small (approx. 80,000 km²)
75 self-governing nation, provides an ideal test case for exploring the dynamics of land use demand

76 variability through afforestation. This is because Scotland has: 1. An ambitious and clearly
77 articulated policy of forest expansion with specific quantified targets for future afforestation
78 (Scottish Government 2018); 2. Wide availability of land use, forestry and land use suitability
79 data; 3. Extensive recent research around forestry expansion, but relatively little quantification of
80 actual forest planting potential (though see, e.g. Ovando et al 2025). In this sense, our case study
81 area allows us to explore the impact of very disruptive, extreme land use demand scenarios in the
82 real world context of planned, ongoing land use change. We use our case study to draw
83 conclusions both for the general, neglected research area around estimation of future land use
84 demand, and offer useful lessons both for futures research in general and forestry policy in
85 Scotland in particular.

86 Specifically, we propose to address the following research questions:

87 RQ1. How much variation is possible in forest land use allocation, if all constraints, except direct
88 physical constraints, are relaxed?

89 RQ2. Under this same assumption, how easy is it, in principle, to meet specific targets for forest
90 expansion?

91 RQ3. Given such potential unpredictability in land use demand for forestry, which land-uses are
92 most at risk, and where?

93 To address these research questions, we developed an integrated land use simulation model with
94 two key components; 1) a forest land allocation model (Section 2.1, below), which assigned new
95 forest planting to the most suitable locations, and 2) a stochastic forest demand model (Section
96 2.2, below) which determined how much forest land should be allocated on the basis of a nature-
97 like evolutionary process chain, where the demand depends only on the previous demand,
98 modified by a stochastic variance term.

99 **2. Methods**

100 *2.1. The land allocation model*

101 To model forest land use allocation, we adapted the SIMLANDER model (Hewitt et al 2013).
102 SIMLANDER takes as its starting point a map of land use (Scottish land use map for 2015,
103 Figure 1), in which the land use of interest (in this case forestry) is assigned value 1 and areas
104 where land of this class could potentially be allocated value 0. A mask layer is applied to ensure
105 that land areas which cannot physically become forest are excluded, i.e. water, urban areas and
106 deep peatlands. As a compromise between landscape detail and computational power, a 200m x
107 200m raster cell size was adopted for all layers.

108

109 Figure 1, Scotland study area, showing afforested areas in 2015 and 2019 according to various
 110 sources. Source: 2015, LCM2007 (Morton et al 2011) updated with woodland inventory (WI)
 111 data for 2010-15 (Patterson et al 2014; Forestry Commission 2015); WI data 2019 (Forestry
 112 Commission 2019). Inset boxes B and C show new afforestation in the Highlands around
 113 Inverness and in the Galloway Forest Park area of southwest Scotland.

114 To run the model, *neighbourhood* weights are applied to the starting map of land use (2015)
 115 through a moving window filter such that non-forest cells close to existing forest cells are given
 116 a higher potential to change to forest land in the next time step than non-forest cells at more
 117 distant locations. The appropriateness of the terrain for forestry, or *suitability*, taken from the
 118 James Hutton Institute's 6-class classification map of land capability (LCF) for forestry (Soil
 119 Survey of Scotland Staff 1988), is also included in the model. A *random variable term* v is added
 120 to the model to ensure that simulations are non-identical, and that unexpected development may
 121 occasionally occur. The random factor follows a right-skewed distribution based on the random
 122 uniform distribution with most values clustered around 1, such that the stochastic factor mostly
 123 has little impact. Modification of the exponent scales the random effect, such that large random

124 effects can be generated if desired. Finally, areas where forest plantation is impossible or not
125 permitted are included in the *zoning* parameter. At each time step $t+1$, neighbourhood (N),
126 randomness (v), suitability (S) and zoning (Z) are computed to produce a total transition
127 potential layer (TTP), P_{ij}^{t+1} in Eqn. 1, as follows.

$$128 \quad P_{ij}^{t+1} = (I_{ij}^{t1} + N_{ij}^t + v_{ij}^t + S_{ij}^t) \cdot Z_{ij}^t \quad (\text{Eqn. 1})$$

129 Where I_{ij}^{t1} represents *inertia*, such that existing woodland areas have a higher TTP than new
130 unplanted areas, N_{ij}^t is the neighbourhood effect at time t , v_{ij}^t is the random factor at time t , S_{ij}^t
131 is suitability at time t and Z_{ij}^t is the zoning layer in which excluded areas take value 0, giving
132 overall TTP values of 0 through multiplication (Figure 2).

133 Forest land is then assigned to the areas where TTP is highest in rank order until the final key
134 parameter, land use *demand*, is satisfied. Land use demand is simply the amount of land (raster
135 cells, 1 cell = 4ha) which the model will allocate. To calibrate the model, neighbourhood weights
136 are adjusted following the procedure described in Roodposhti et al (2020), running the model
137 each time from one known year (e.g. 2015) to another (e.g. 2019). For calibration, land use
138 demand is simply equal to the total forest area in the second map i.e. 2019. The calibration
139 results are compared visually and statistically against a range of metrics which evaluate the cell-
140 by-cell coincidence and the pattern similarity between the real and the simulated land use
141 configurations. However, the procedure is not exact and is not intended to produce a “best
142 model” (Hewitt et al 2022), rather it is intended to show that the model generates forest land use
143 patterns that are acceptably similar to existing land use. Detailed model technical specifications,
144 calibration results and scripts are provided in [Supplementary Material](#) (S1.1 to S1.4).

145 Once the model is calibrated, it is ready to be run forward to allocate land for future years. To do
146 this, future land use demand must be estimated for the desired future date. For example, urban
147 land use demand can be calculated using population projections (see e.g. Hewitt and Díaz-
148 Pacheco 2017), agriculture or forest land use demand can be estimated following tendencies
149 derived from model scenarios, e.g. using Integrated Assessment Model projections, or by
150 following predetermined trajectories, e.g. from Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (Hewitt et al
151 2020). However, as we argue in this paper, these static approaches do not account for the full
152 range of variability in land use change that may actually occur. Further, if we use policy targets
153 as land use demand estimates, for example, the existing forestry projections set down in
154 Scotland's Forestry Strategy (Scottish Government 2018), we would be unable to evaluate either
155 the expected variability in forest expansion (RQ1) or the feasibility of these policy targets (RQ2).

156 2.2 *The stochastic forest demand model*

157 To solve this problem, we instead determine the land use demand for forestry year-on-year on the
158 basis of a simulated process chain which follows a stochastic pattern of variability. Such a
159 pattern of variability could be considered analogous to a market-based instrument such as a

160 carbon price, a subsidy or certification scheme for land use conversion, or some other form of
161 incentive, such as a policy directive. In our case we use a Markov Chain, with annual demand
162 determined solely by incremental stochastic variation on the previous year (Eqn. 2). Despite its
163 apparent simplicity, demand modelled in this way exhibits enormous variation, analogous to
164 stock markets, board games played with dice, weather predictions, bacteria reproduction, and
165 many other things (Browne et al 2024).

166 Formally, we model land use demand, Δ_n , as a random walk:

$$167 \quad \Delta_n = \Delta_{n-1} \cdot X_n, \quad n \geq 1 \quad (\text{Eqn. 2})$$

168 Where X_n is a percentage annual adjustment, set at 100% at when the model is initiated, and
169 calculated thereafter by the sum of the previous value of X_n , X_{n-1} and the annual stochastic
170 adjustment, which takes, with equal probability (Pr), a value of +1 or -1 (Eqn 3)

$$171 \quad X_n = X_{n-1} + A_1 \quad (\text{Eqn. 3})$$

172 Where:

$$173 \quad \Pr(A_1 = 1) = \Pr(A_1 = -1) = 0.5$$

174
175 This is analogous to the classic case of the symmetric random walk known as the *drunkards walk*
176 (Pearson 1905). By using this function to determine land use demand at each time step and then
177 allocating this demand as described above in the land allocation model, we were able to explore,
178 through a multiple run Monte Carlo simulation, the extent of the variation possible in our study
179 case. We chose a simulation run period of 100 years, from the 2015 initial map up to the year
180 2115, sufficient to allow markedly different land allocation trajectories to play out fully. Initial
181 land use demand was set to the existing Scottish Government (2018) annual afforestation policy
182 target of 10,000 ha per year. The policy in fact states ambition to escalate afforestation from
183 10,000 ha a year in 2018 to 12,000 ha per year in 2020/21, 14,000 ha per year in 2022/23 up to
184 15,000 ha per year after 2024/25.

185
186 The stochastic land use demand simulator (Eqn 2, 3) then works to modify the target demands
187 on an annual basis by applying a uniform pseudorandom adjustment of $\pm 1\%$ or $\pm 5\%$ in order to
188 reflect the strength of the incentive to plant, translated into higher or lower land allocation. Thus
189 if 10,000 ha of land are to be allocated under a full allocation scenario, a variation of 1% will
190 lead to 10,100- or 9,900-hectare allocations, depending on the direction of that variation. At the
191 key target years 2018, 2020, 2022 and 2024, we assume a policy intervention ensuring full
192 allocation in line with targets for those years. However, the stochastic adjustment is not reset for
193 the target years, representing the fact that, in the real world, even dramatic policy interventions
194 must take place within the wider socioeconomic policy context. The model's Markov property, in
195 which each year's land allocation depends only on the existing allocation at the start of that year

196 (with the exception of the four target years), allowed for a great variety of stochastic fluctuations,
197 including continuous linear, power law or exponential growth or decay, rises and falls from peaks
198 or troughs, or metastable oscillations around the baseline demand.

199
200 Forest removal¹ and windfall/fire was not modelled, so even under the most pessimistic
201 conditions of virtually zero annual forest expansion, maintenance of existing forest was assumed.
202 Forest growth was limited only by the suitable area, such that, under the most extreme examples
203 of a forest planting boom, forest expansion ceased only once every cell of land area of even
204 marginal suitability for forestry had been filled. Unsuitable forest areas included large urban
205 areas, lochs (water bodies) and areas of deep peatland recorded in the “Land unsuitable for trees”
206 category of the LCF map (Soil Survey of Scotland Staff 1988). The stochastic land use demand
207 simulator R script is provided in [Supplementary Material](#) (S1.4). Figure 2 shows the complete
208 model workflow.

¹ When land is afforested, permission is required before it can be felled (Scottish Forestry 2024).

209
210

Figure 2: Full model workflow, model parameters and Transition Potential equation (Eqn. 1)

211 The land use simulation model was then run from 2015 forward to 2115 (100 years) to simulate
 212 forest allocation under new forest planting demand scenarios generated by the stochastic demand
 213 model. The simulation was run 100 times for each of the two forest demand models (stochastic
 214 variation of 1%; stochastic variation of 5%) giving sufficient data to examine the diversity of
 215 possible land use responses over the given period. Results of the demand model for each
 216 stochastic variation case are provided in [Supplementary Material](#) (S1.5). Each 100-year run in
 217 the Monte Carlo test ensemble was entirely independent of every other run, with demand model
 218 results being numbered sequentially in order of execution (e.g. simulation 1 (Sim 1), simulation
 219 2 (Sim 2) ..., simulation 32 (Sim 32) etc.).

220 Finally, model simulation results were compared with land use in 2015 using a map overlay
 221 technique known as cross-tabulation (see, e.g. Cox 1992). This allowed us to estimate the
 222 percentage of each land use in 2015 projected to be converted to forest land in 2050.

223 3. Results

224 3.1 Allocation responses to stochastically evolving forest demand (RQ1, RQ2).

225 In the following section, we discuss the land use outcomes based on the different land use
 226 allocation outcomes that emerged from the demand model ([Supplementary Material](#), Tables S2
 227 and S3).

228 First, we turn our attention to the Scottish government policy target of 21% of Scotland’s total
 229 land area occupied by woodland by 2032. In the simplest terms, the target is physically attainable
 230 with the considered spatial constraints, since the largest possible amount of forestry that can be
 231 allocated in Scotland is 54,138.12 km² out of a total land area of 77,935 km² (Table 1), or 69.47%
 232 of the total land area of Scotland. However, this is an extremely unrealistic and unlikely
 233 outcome, since it would imply the occupation of all land except the areas specifically designated
 234 as unsuitable according to the James Hutton Institute land capability for forestry map (Soil
 235 Survey of Scotland Staff 1988). These unsuitable areas include large urban areas, lochs, rocky
 236 mountain tops and peatlands.

237 The first thing to note is that allocation of 10,000 ha a year is not enough to meet the 2032 target,
 238 achieving afforestation on only around 19% of Scotland’s land area, no modelling is required to
 239 see this. Neither is the escalating ambition reflected by the Scottish Government policy targets
 240 for 2018, 2020, 2022 and 2024 enough to achieve this figure, though it comes close, achieving
 241 20% of the total land area in 2032 (Table 1).

Year	Accumulated hectares of woodland	New woodland hectares planned per year	Accumulated % of woodland in Scotland
2015	1,350,196	10,000	17.3
2016	1,360,196	10,000	17.5
2017	1,370,196	10,000	17.6

2018	1,380,196	10,000	17.7
2019	1,390,196	10,000	17.8
2020	1,400,196	12,000	18.0
2021	1,412,196	12,000	18.1
2022	1,424,196	14,000	18.3
2023	1,438,196	14,000	18.5
2024	1,452,196	15,000	18.6
2025	1,467,196	15,000	18.8
2026	1,482,196	15,000	19.0
2027	1,497,196	15,000	19.2
2028	1,512,196	15,000	19.4
2029	1,527,196	15,000	19.6
2030	1,542,196	15,000	19.8
2031	1,557,196	15,000	20.0
2032	1,572,196	15,000	20.2

242 Table 1: Hectares of woodland planned under Scotland’s Forestry Strategy 2019-29. Percentages
243 out of 7,793,500 ha land area from 2015 land cover map, excluding inland waters. E.g.
244 $(1,350,196/7,793,500)*100=17.319$.

245 *3.1.1 Model 1: 1% Stochastic variation*

246 It was therefore interesting to see if the assumption of a stochastic variation of 1% might offer
247 some possibility that existing targets could be achieved. The results are discussed as follows,
248 with reference to the individual simulations for 2015-2115 from the 100 run Monte Carlo test (S1
249 to S100; simulation numbers are arbitrary labels with no meaning other than the order of
250 execution).

251

252 Figure 3: A (top left): Markovian land use demand evolution of the 1% simulations with the five
 253 highest land allocation outcomes by 2032 (orange-red lines) and the five lowest land allocation
 254 outcomes by 2032. (blue-grey lines). The year 2032 is indicated by the vertical red line. Figure
 255 3B (top right): atypical or unusual patterns. Sim 32 (in red) shows the trajectory which attained
 256 the highest land use demand out of all simulations; sim 34 (blue), the lowest. Sim 65 (blue grey)

257 and Sim 88 (dark red) are the inverse of each other, showing, respectively, rapid demand growth
258 followed by steady decline, and rapid collapse followed by gradual recovery. Figure 3C
259 (bottom): Markovian land use demand evolution of the 5% simulations with the five highest land
260 allocation outcomes by 2032 (orange-red lines) and the five lowest land allocation outcomes by
261 2032 (blue-grey lines). The year 2032 is indicated by the vertical red line. The lowest and highest
262 land allocations for 2032 in the 1% case (see Figure 3B) are shown for reference (grey dashed
263 lines).

264 Figure 3A shows the overall land use demand evolution of the 1% simulations with the highest
265 and lowest land allocation outcomes for the year 2032. Note that some simulations which
266 produced low land allocation outcomes in 2032, later recovered dramatically (e.g. Sim 30, cyan
267 line), while some that produced very high initial land allocation outcomes later saw a severe
268 demand collapse (e.g. Sim 27, yellow line). Figure 3B illustrates the extremes of the
269 distribution, with a complete land use demand collapse (Sim 34, blue line), down to a lowest
270 point of 69% demand adjustment (allocation falling below 10 ha/year after 2070), and
271 conversely, an unstoppable boom (Sim 32, red line), with a high of 126% demand adjustment of
272 leading to an obviously extremely improbable 61% of Scotland under forestry by 2050.

273 Figure 4 shows the percentage of total land area in Scotland allocated to forestry at each of the
274 four key milestone dates: 2032, 2050, 2070, 2115, for 100 model runs for the years 2015-2115
275 under both 1% and 5% stochastic model variants. Despite the enormous variation observed in the
276 model results, the stated target of 21% of land area under forestry by 2032 was achieved in the
277 1% variation model on only two occasions (Figure 4A). However, by 2050, the target had been
278 met in 92 of 100 simulations, rising to 96 in 2070 and 96 in 2115.

280 Figure 4: Percentage of total land area in Scotland allocated to forestry (y axis) under existing
281 targets at each of the four key milestone dates: 2032, 2050, 2070, 2115, for 100 model runs for
282 the years 2015-2115 under a stochastic variation term of 1% (Top row: A, zoomed inset right);
283 and under a stochastic variation term of 5% (Bottom row: B, zoomed inset right). The horizontal
284 blue line represents 21% of Scotland's total land area. Model allocation amounts beyond the
285 available land use in Scotland (green line) cannot be allocated in the land use model.

286 3.1.2 Model 2: 5% Stochastic variation

287 By changing the stochastic variation term to 5%, the 2032 target was met (or overshot) more
288 frequently. This was the case of simulation 49, 8, 32, and 2, for example (Figure 3C). However,
289 this kind of extreme demand growth occurred < 25% of the time (Figure 4B).

290 However, the drawback of such an approach is that the Markovian demand function is stochastic,
291 and demand can also crash. This is the case of simulations 24, 83, 12, 45, and 31 (Figure 3C).
292 Sim 45 and 31 (Figure 3C) are instructive, since in both simulations forestry demand recovers
293 from the early crash, even, in the case of Sim 45, apparently attaining a metastable plateau for
294 ~30 years between 2060 and 2090, with a demand adjustment of around 75-80%. Alas, the
295 damage has been done, and no new forest planting will take place. Once forest demand has
296 fallen to zero (in Sim 45 this occurred around 2035) under this model, recovery is impossible,
297 since 5% increments or decrements of zero remain zero. This could potentially be modified in
298 future versions of the model, by "restarting" forest demand after zero is reached at a random
299 value. This does, however, raise the question of whether such an assumption is reasonable in a
300 scenario of total demand collapse.

301 Further, we can see that due to the model's Markov property (memoryless, such that future
302 evolution is independent of historical evolution), initial demand boom can also turn dramatically
303 to bust. This is the case of Sim 41 (Figure 3C, red line), which accelerates dramatically to meet
304 the 2032 target, before suddenly plunging (around 2040), a tendency that turns into a severe
305 long-term decline.

306 It is also interesting to observe that though cases of rapid and continuous demand collapse did
307 occur (e.g. simulation 24, Figure 3C), this was not a necessary factor in failure to achieve the
308 2032 target or to drive long term forest expansion. Simulation 47, for example, shows that, in a
309 stochastically evolving demand system with such high levels of annual variation, even a period
310 of mild early uncertainty can render targets unachievable. Indeed, as Figure 3D clearly shows,
311 the most likely outcome under these conditions is still a failure to meet the targets.

312 Under the 5% stochastic variation model, while more simulations meet the 21% target by 2032
313 than under the 1% stochastic variation model, more simulations also fail to meet the 21% target
314 by 2050, 2070 and 2115 than under the 1% stochastic variation model. Only 59 of 100
315 simulations achieved 21% or greater forest cover by 2050, rising to 62 in 2070 and 67 in 2115.

316 Hence, while increasing the stochastic variation increases the chances of meeting the allocation
317 targets at the earliest date (2032), it also increases the chance of not meeting them at all.

318 3.2 *Land use occupation under extensive afforestation.*

319 The model is unconstrained, such that the most extreme allocation outcomes led to the complete
320 occupation of all even marginally capable land in Scotland by 2115 (Figure 5). This is not a
321 likely outcome under any circumstances since it would imply the complete loss of all agricultural
322 land. Of much greater relevance and interest, however, is the range of possible allocation
323 outcomes by 2032 and 2050, we explore these in the following section.

324
325 Figure 5: Map of forest land allocation in 2015, 2032 and 2050 under the 1% stochastic variation
326 scenario, for the two highest scoring (most forest land allocated) simulations. The left-hand
327 simulation (Sim 32) is an outlier and is useful only as an illustration of the extent of the
328 maximum available area for forestry. The right-hand simulation (Sim 84) shows 35.5% of the
329 total area of Scotland under forestry, an extreme, but more plausible scenario.

330 Figure 6 shows the land uses in 2015 that coincide with areas of projected forest expansion in
331 2050, according to the ten highest allocation simulations for the 1% stochastic variation model.
332 In the CA model, the most powerful driver of allocation is proximity to existing land use of the
333 same type. It is not surprising, therefore, that the largest amounts of future forest land are
334 adjacent to existing forest stands, especially conifers. Next, we see that these results also
335 highlight the *priority order* that land would hypothetically be converted to forestry as available
336 land is exhausted. For example, in Sim 84, we see that the most favoured land use, after existing
337 forest areas, is *improved grasslands* (impgrass), with >7,000 km² converting to forestry, just
338 under half of the existing total (the 2015 land use map records 14,815 km² of improved
339 grassland). Croplands are also quickly occupied by new woodland, and under the most extreme
340 case of out-of-control forest planting fever represented by Sim 32, are almost completely
341 colonized, leaving virtually no arable land at all, with 6,624 km² occupied, out of a total of 6,807
342 km² under all arable (horticulture, cereals and potatoes) together. Finally, once all other lands are
343 used up, natural and semi-natural categories (semi-natural grassland, mountain heath, and bog)
344 become highly vulnerable. However, it is also noticeable that some less extreme forest planting
345 scenarios (e.g. Sim 52), do also colonize these sensitive natural areas to some extent. This is not
346 as surprising as it may at first seem, for two reasons. First, while natural protected areas and
347 registered areas of deep peatland were excluded from the model, these three natural and semi-
348 natural land cover classes record sensitive organic soils that do not have special protection, and
349 are, at least in principle, available for afforestation (even if they may not be suitable for carbon
350 sequestration purposes, Baggio-Compagnucci et al, 2022). Second, currently afforested areas
351 tend to occupy agriculturally marginal lands, which, by their nature are adjacent to natural and
352 semi-natural areas.

353

Land cover area and category occupied by woodland under each simulation (barplot, left) and total woodland area (map, right) in each simulation. **10 highest allocation simulations under the 1% stochastic variation scenario..**

355 Figure 6: Results of map overlay analysis between land use 2015 and simulated forest land use in
 356 2050, 1% variation model, **10 highest allocation simulations**. Y axis in km². NB: ALL forest
 357 land is allocated at each time step (e.g. under a 10ha per year location, 100 ha allocated at t1, 110
 358 ha allocated at t2, 120 ha allocated at t3 etc). This figure shows the land use categories in 2015
 359 which have become forest by 2050. The *model* does not differentiate between broadleaved and
 360 conifer, unlike the land use map 2015 with which it has been overlain.

361 Clearly, if the historical pattern of forestry expansion onto adjacent areas is respected, improved
 362 grasslands are likely to be occupied first, followed by arable land. However, some erosion of
 363 natural areas is likely to take place at the forest margins. Though very extreme forest expansion
 364 scenarios like Sim 32 are eye-catching (Figure 5), it is the less extreme scenarios, for example
 365 Sim 52, which are potentially more illuminating. In Sim 52, 29% of the total area of Scotland is
 366 afforested by 2050, clearly a very large amount, but perhaps not implausibly large, given the
 367 scale of the carbon mitigation challenge. The 2015 map records 13,502 km² under forestry, Sim
 368 52 would entail 22,976 km², an increase of approximately 70%. But at what cost?

Land use name	Non-Forest (Km²)	Forest (Km²)	<i>Land use group name</i>	<i>Non-Forest Group total (Km²)</i>	<i>Forest Group total (Km²)</i>	<i>% Land use group afforested</i>
Semi-natural Grass-land	12284	952				
Mountain Heath	18984	741				
Peat bogs	7429	114	Natural and semi-natural	38697	1807	4.5
Urban and built-up areas	1095	235	Urban	1095	235	17.7
Improved Grassland	10126	4689	Pasture	10126	4689	31.7
Horticulture	810	799				
Cereal crops	2474	2452				
Potatoes	103	169	Arable	3387	3420	50.2
Broadleaved woodland	380	2817				
Coniferous woodland	420	9886	Forest	799	12702	94.1*
Salt water	494	5				
Fresh water	1587	96				
Coastal Areas	977	22	Water and coastal	3058	122	3.8
Total				57162	22976	
Scotland area (excl Salt and Fresh Water)				77935		
				30		

369

370 Table 2: Results of map overlay analysis between land use 2015 and simulated forest land in
371 Simulation 52. *See in text discussion on this point.

372 Table 2 shows how this simulation would impact on existing land uses (2015). The figures for
373 built-up land can be safely discounted, since the allocation of new forest to this category is due to
374 the imprecision of the layer mask around urban areas. Though in practice no new forest land
375 would occur here, this result is unsurprising since areas that are suitable for urban land may also
376 be suitable for forestry. It is notable that while the land intake from improved grassland is much
377 larger by area than from cropland, it is a smaller percentage of the total area of this land use class
378 (32%, as opposed to 50% of all arable). Remembering that the CA model allocates new forest
379 land mostly on the basis of proximity, this would seem to be due to the fact that there is a lot of
380 cropland adjacent to established forest areas that can be quite easily afforested. For economic as
381 well as cultural and societal reasons, of course, this is extremely unlikely to happen in the
382 absence of a major shift in the value of forest with respect to arable land. It is also notable that
383 not all existing forest land (94%) remained under forest in 2050, because adjacent areas were
384 found by the model to be more suitable than existing areas in some cases. There has also been
385 some encroachment of forest plantation on riverine and coastal habitats, which might be
386 considered undesirable from a conservation point of view.

387 We can now adjust the figures in this table to exclude afforestation in these various undesirable
388 cases and recalculate the total land areas (Table 3)

Land use name	Non-Forest (Km²)	Forest (Km²)	<i>Land use group name</i>	<i>Non-Forest Group total (Km²)</i>	<i>Forest Group total (Km²)</i>	<i>% Land use group afforested</i>
Semi-natural Grassland	13237	0				
Mountain Heath	19725	0				
Peat bogs	7543	0	Natural and semi-natural	40504	0	0
Urban and built-up areas	1330	0	Urban	1330	0	0
Improved Grassland	10126	4689	Pasture	10126	4689	32
Horticulture	1609	0				
Cereal crops	4926	0				
Potatoes	272	0	Arable	6807	0	0
Broadleaved woodland	0	3196				

Coniferous wood-land	0	10306	Forest	0	13502	100
Salt water	499	0				
Fresh water	1683	0				
Coastal Areas	999	0	Water and coastal	3180	0	0
Total				61947	18191	
Scotland area (excl Salt and Fresh Water)					76958	
% of Scotland afforested (18191/77935*100)					23.34	

389

390 Table 3: Results of map overlay analysis between land use 2015 and simulated forest land in
391 Simulation 52, adjusted to remove afforestation on areas likely to be undesirable from planning,
392 conservation, or agricultural reasons.

393 Under this scenario (Table 3), the amount of afforested land in 2050 would fall to 18,191 km², a
394 more plausible sounding increase of approximately 35% with respect to 2015. If we ensure that
395 no forest expansion is permitted on natural and semi-natural areas, urban areas, cropland or river
396 and coastal areas, and that existing forest land classes are fully occupied by forest in 2050, it
397 would be possible to increase the total afforested area to 22.7% of the total land area Scotland. If
398 we exclude all water bodies from the total land area, to avoid ambiguity around what constitutes
399 Scotland's land area, this total rises to 23.34%. Of course, this still entails a loss of 32% of
400 existing improved grassland, which might not be acceptable in any case. And thus, the only
401 conceivable way of exceeding 23.34% of Scotland's land area under forest, without encroaching
402 on natural or semi natural areas, urban areas, cropland, or coastal areas, would be to plant on
403 improved grassland. To carry this argument to its logical conclusion, we now see that if all
404 improved grassland in Scotland (14,815 km²) were converted to forest, the total afforested area
405 would increase by a further 10,126 km², to a total of 28,317 km². This equates to 37% of
406 Scotland's land area under forest, being the limit beyond which arable land or natural areas
407 would have to be converted. Conversion of all arable land in Scotland would supply another
408 6,807 km² enabling a total of 35,124 km², equivalent to 46% of Scotland's land area under forest.
409 Realistically, since such significant declines to farmland (either pasture or arable) are unlikely to
410 be contemplated in the near future, around 23% of Scotland's total land area is likely to be the
411 maximum possible amount that could ever plausibly be assigned to forestry use. Only under
412 scenarios that contemplate massive conversion of grazing or arable land, as well as significant
413 risk of loss of marginal natural and semi-natural areas could this total be exceeded.

414 4. Discussion

415 4.1 The importance of simulating extreme variability in land-use outcomes

416 Conventional land use models typically seek to understand how much land would be allocated to
417 a particular use given certain known drivers, or, where specific land uses would be most likely
418 allocated given land use demands estimated from policy targets, desired outcomes or
419 demographic projections. The work we present in the paper offers a critical counterpoint to these
420 approaches. Our model shows how initially quite plausible tendencies can rapidly scale into very
421 extreme outcomes.

422 For our example case of forest planting in Scotland, results show both very extreme outcomes
423 (1% Sim 32) as well as more plausible ones (1% Sim 52). In the model, any land that is not
424 actively excluded (deep peatland, water, urban areas) can in principle be afforested. In reality, the
425 land system has limits (bio-physical, cultural, societal, economic or policy) which would prevent
426 such outcomes. However, it is not certain exactly where these limits may lie. While we accept
427 that some of these are implausible, history shows that very extreme land use outcomes do occur,
428 as, with the major expansion of agricultural land in the UK following the Agriculture Act of 1947
429 (Robinson and Sutherland 2002), the emergence of vast areas of intensive crop cultivation like
430 the “sea of plastic” of Almeria (Castillo-Díaz et al 2021), and the recognised problem of urban
431 sprawl (Kasanko et al 2006). These transformations of the land system are often unforeseen and
432 have surprising and even catastrophic consequences. The exploratory nature of the model thus
433 allows us to explore open-ended outcomes which more conventional approaches do not consider.

434 For the specific case of Scotland’s forest policy, we show that neither continuous stable
435 expansion at the targeted levels, nor stochastic increases on the targeted levels in the 1% model
436 were able to meet the targeted 21% of all land area by the specified date of 2032 in the vast
437 majority of cases. However, in >75% of cases, these targets were achieved by 2050 (Figure 4A).
438 Increasing stochastic variation to 5% led to a greater chance of achieving the 21% target by 2032
439 (about a quarter of the time, Fig 4B), but also increased the chances of this target being missed
440 even over longer periods of time. In short, extreme instability in the stochastic system cuts both
441 ways.

442 One potential example of a system that might exhibit this kind of behaviour is the case where
443 land use allocation is tied to the dynamics of markets. Though the saying “what goes up must
444 come down” is something of a cliché, it is demonstrably true in the case of markets, and
445 frequently the timing of boom and bust-like behaviour is unpredictable (Koutmos et al. 1993).
446 This is likely to be especially the case for subsidised land allocation related to climate mitigation,
447 since the policy context is contested and subject to sharp shocks and reversals, related to the
448 changing political fortunes of particular governments or factions. At the same time, the process is
449 not well-supported by high quality information, for example, relating to the suitability of specific
450 soils for key tree species under climate change (Baggio-Compagnucci et al 2022) or different
451 economic assumptions (Ovando et al 2025).

452 The central contribution of our work is to reproduce, in a computational model, these kinds of
453 behaviours, in which many variables conspire to produce system-wide fluctuations and shocks,

454 and to show how this can affect the land system in surprising ways. In this sense we build on
455 earlier work (Hewitt et al 2017, Kovalevsky et al 2017) which introduced dynamical systems
456 approaches into a cellular automata land allocation model (APoLUS). In this earlier research,
457 both the suitability of particular land areas as well as the amount of land to be allocated was
458 affected by the behaviour of key actors (e.g. landowners, policy makers) whose interactions
459 worked to enhance or reduce the favourability of particular land use types. As these authors
460 observed, “Policy makers are keen not just to know ‘where’ future developments are likely to
461 occur, but also on what timescale they are likely to take place, given certain conditions.” (Hewitt
462 et al 2017). The stochastic land allocation model we present here is useful precisely because it
463 addresses both these key elements, and in this sense, moves beyond state-of-the-art to show how
464 high level land use change targets may have unintended consequences, especially if policy
465 uncertainty is high, or market-based incentives are expected to deliver the desired outcome with
466 minimal intervention. In our experimental case, these consequences range from complete policy
467 failure (the 2032 target is never met at all) to extremely delayed success (targets met much later
468 than anticipated), to a gold-rush type scenario, in which every possible square meter of land is
469 allocated to forest, with important negative consequences for national food security. Though our
470 model deliberately takes these dynamics to the extreme, there are many good examples of
471 policies that, although designed to promote an essential service, incentivize a desired system
472 transformation or promote a key public good, had extremely serious and unanticipated negative
473 consequences. Three such cases can be highlighted, as follows.

474 The first case is perhaps the best known internationally. As a response to the oil-shocks of the
475 1970s, a number of countries, most prominently Brazil, began growing crops such as sugarcane
476 and maize (corn) for conversion into bioethanol for use as a motor fuel (Rathmann et al 2010).
477 The availability of generous subsidies led bioenergy crops to displace food production, raised the
478 price of agricultural land, and incentivized the conversion of native ecosystems through cropland
479 expansion (Fargione et al 2008). In this latter case, this led to a *carbon debt*, whereby the CO₂
480 released from land clearance was greater than the emissions avoided from the use of non-fossil
481 fuels. Similar concerns have been raised about forest planting for carbon sequestration, namely,
482 that mechanised planting approaches may release more CO₂ than is captured over the lifetime of
483 the tree (Baggio-Compagnucci et al 2022). It is concerning that similar dynamics to those
484 already observed in the case of biofuels over forty years ago (Brown 1980) are again playing out
485 in the context of forestry.

486 For the second case, we turn to Spain, where the national 2008 regulation on solar photovoltaic
487 installations (Royal Decree 1578/2008) created a boom-and-bust cycle, leading to initial
488 explosive growth of solar PV, followed by hasty control measures and resulting undesirable
489 consequences, including hugely inflated public costs and subsequent investor flight (Del Río and
490 Mir-Artígues 2012). At the same time, the rapid expansion of vast solar parks in traditional
491 agricultural areas, such as Mentrída, a well-known wine-growing region of Toledo, has had
492 major local land use impacts, and sparked intense conflict and the emergence of local resistance

493 movements (Romero 2022, Portillo and Jimenez 2021). Better foresight analysis of economic
494 and land use impacts of this kind of explosive expansion could have avoided such outcomes.

495 In a third case, the United Kingdom’s post-second world war drive to achieve self-sufficiency in
496 food production, which accelerated with accession to the EU in 1973, is now recognised to have
497 had major negative impacts on biodiversity (Robinson and Sutherland 2002). This was largely a
498 result of consolidation of farms into ever larger holdings, with elimination of wildlife-rich
499 hedgerows, and intensification and mechanisation leading to enormous yield increases at the
500 expense of vegetation and ecosystem health. In the context of its time, this was seen as a great
501 success (Blundell 2000), and it is doubtful if better foresight would have achieved a different
502 outcome. The ongoing agricultural reforms in the UK, in particular, England’s Environmental
503 Land Management programme (ELM) (DEFRA 2023), and the Agriculture and Rural
504 Communities (Scotland) Act 2024, which replace the Common Agricultural Policy following the
505 UK’s departure from the EU, finally offer a window of opportunity to begin to undo some of the
506 damage. Extreme “disruptive” scenarios of land use outcomes, like those explored in this piece,
507 could offer useful insights to help avoid the long-lasting unintended consequences of previous
508 agricultural policies.

509 The possibility of these kinds of expensive unintended consequences, and the serious risks of
510 major environmental impacts, suggests that incentive schemes for large scale land use change,
511 like renewable energy development, afforestation, new towns, intensive greenhouse agriculture,
512 *inter alia* need to be more carefully designed than has historically been the case. The three
513 examples cited above can provide instructive lessons for situations like the present case of
514 Scotland, where fixed policy targets are expected to drive land use change, but where little
515 serious thought has been given to the potential for feedbacks and unforeseen outcomes.

516 **4.2 Limitations and future work**

517 In our model, we treat land use demand as ahistorical; such that land use depends only on
518 demand in the previous year, not on its historical evolution, enabling the use of the Markov chain
519 approach. This might be considered an unrealistic assumption. However, we would advocate this
520 approach primarily in an exploratory context where many interacting and unknown variables are
521 at play in the land system. There is a long tradition in mathematics and statistics of using
522 stochasticity to approximate the behaviour of dynamical systems when the underlying variables
523 are too numerous, or too poorly understood for direct calculation; this is the foundation of the
524 Monte Carlo method (Metropolis and Ulam 1949), cellular automata (Ulam 1952, Von Neumann
525 and Burks 1966) and numerous other schools of thought aligned with the theory of complex
526 systems (see e.g. Prigogine and Stengers 1997, Mandelbrot 1983, *inter alia*).

527 Even if we accept the utility of the Markovian stochastic approach we follow here, it is clear that
528 improvements could be made to our simple model. The two tested ranges of stochastic variation
529 (1% and 5%) were arbitrarily chosen to demonstrate the utility of the model. An interesting
530 challenge for future work might be to try to estimate the degree of variation in some historical

531 observed system (the carbon price, renewable energy expansion) and project such a system
532 forward using the Markov Chain approach applied here. The introduction of even quite small
533 annual stochastic variations in a demand model of this kind is likely to reproduce more realistic
534 behaviour than the conventional assumption of incremental linear land-use growth or decay over
535 time.

536 In our study case of Scotland, we have not considered either the feasibility of forest expansion in
537 terms of the relative suitability (biophysical or economic) of potentially available land, or the
538 much-discussed question of whether reducing livestock numbers (and hence their emissions)
539 might allow for less ambitious forest planting targets. These aspects are discussed in two recent
540 papers (Ovando et al 2025, Gimona et al 2026), and deserve further consideration in future work.

541 **5. Conclusions**

542 A stochastic Markov Chain model was coupled to a cellular automata land allocation model to
543 simulate the effect of fluctuating land use demand for the case of forest planting in Scotland, UK.
544 In the simulations, the existing policy target for forest planting (21% of Scotland's land area
545 under forest) was rarely met by the specified date (2032) but was frequently met by 2050. The
546 stochastic model shows how an unexpectedly large range of variation can emerge from initially
547 plausible outcomes, such as a forest planting boom, leading to loss of cropland or natural areas,
548 or alternatively a collapse in planting rates, and policy failure. For the specific case of Scotland,
549 our model suggests that new forest planting is likely to expand preferentially onto improved
550 grasslands and cereals, and to a lesser extent on other arable cropland and at semi-natural forest
551 margins. At the same time, the model indicates that there is abundant space in the land system,
552 without harming natural areas, if arable and pastureland are released for planting. However, if
553 these land areas remain unavailable to foresters, ~23% of Scotland's total land area is likely to be
554 an upper limit for afforestation without incurring damage to natural areas or releasing carbon
555 from planting on organic soils. This is significantly lower than the estimate of 29% offered by
556 Burke et al., (2021). However, Baggio-Campagnucci et al (2022) suggest that Burke et al's figure
557 may be an over-estimate, an assertion our model would seem to support. These results clearly
558 demonstrate the utility of the approach we describe, which seeks to define acceptable bounds of
559 land use expansion within all possible outcomes, rather than estimating likely quantity and
560 location, or likely location given some estimated quantity.

561 Our experimental results suggest that policies to directly drive large scale land use expansion,
562 e.g, by setting fixed targets or offering financial incentives for land use conversion need to be
563 carefully designed in order to avoid negative unintended consequences. Currently, spatially
564 explicit models of future land use change mostly simulate stepwise incremental adjustments to
565 the land system rather than extreme land use change outcomes. This may be because extreme
566 outcomes like those we discussed in this paper are seen as unrealistic or implausible, and in
567 delivering advice to policy, land use modellers need to appear sensible and sober. We argue that
568 such sobriety is misplaced – land use simulations need more drunken walking of the kind we

569 explore in this paper. History shows that land use change can be rapid and wildly disruptive,
570 especially where subsidies are offered, planning laws are too weak to prevent systematic abuses,
571 or where land systems are disrupted by armed conflict. Land use models can help, but they
572 should be treated less as quantitative box-ticking exercises and more as virtual laboratories for
573 genuinely experimental future visioning. Only in this way can we hope to foresee, and
574 adequately prepare for, land use disasters that devastate ecosystems or plunge national
575 economies into recession.

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